

DESIGN AND NON-STRUCTURAL PROPERTIES OF COMPOSITE
MATERIALS

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Introduction

The electrical, magnetic, optical and thermal properties of composite materials discussed in recent years (1-10) mostly concern in situ composites. These are composites grown in a one-step process in which the resulting two-phase structure proceeds from a eutectic melt by cooling down, or by means of a disproportionation reaction in the solid state such as spinodal decomposition, eutectoid decomposition, precipitation from a supersaturated solid solution (11) growth from the vitreous state (12) etc. The main lines of these discussions are equally valid for composite materials obtained by artificial mixing of two (preshaped) substances which may or may not be subjected to subsequent sintering processes or chemical reactions.

Two categories of properties can be distinguished. The first includes the combination-type properties, which can be divided into sum properties and product

properties. Sum properties are those in which the properties of the constituent phases contribute proportionally. Examples are heat conduction, specific density and elastic modulus. Product properties are those in which the physical output of one phase acts as the input of the other phase (8). Examples will be given in section 2.

The second category represents the properties that depend on the morphology of the composite, such as periodicity and anisotropy of the microstructure, the shape and the smallness of the phases and the presence of a large interface between the finely interwoven phases. Examples are the interference colours of light reflected from the surface of a Co-Co₂Si eutectoid composite sample (13), the aligned Si-CrSi₂ eutectic composite consisting of metallic CrSi₂ fibres in a semiconducting matrix of Si and exhibiting a 10⁴ higher electrical conductivity parallel to the fibres than perpendicular to them (14), the observation that the London-Van der Waals constant of 2x10⁻⁶ cm diameter gold particles is a factor of 10 smaller than the value for bulk material (15), and the nonlinear voltage current characteristic of the sintered ZnO-Bi₂O₃ composite material (16). Section 3 will be devoted to this category.

Product properties

Any physical property of a material can be considered as the action of a physical input quantity X producing a physical output quantity Y. This property can be defined as a Y/X effect. In a composite material the constituent phases have their own set Y/X effects for all possible physical quantities. A Z/X composite property that results from a Y/X

effect in the one phase and a Z/Y effect in the other phase, the quantity Y being transferred from the one phase to the other phase by whatever mechanism, is defined as a product property ($Y/X \cdot Z/Y = Z/X$).

This product property may be a completely new one or it may represent a known conversion, but with a higher yield. Two typical realizations will be discussed : the enhanced conversion in X-ray fluorescence screens and the conversion of a magnetic signal into an electrical signal.

Enhanced conversion of X-rays into visible light in thin composite layers

This enhanced conversion has been demonstrated on composite anthracene - $PbCl_2$ screens (17).

Organic substances, such as anthracene, are in use as scintillators to detect high-energy particles and quanta. An anthracene crystal converts X-rays into visible light near UV. The luminescent radiation output is proportional to the absorption of the X-rays during which secondary electrons are released which cause a transition of anthracene molecules from the ground state to excited states that can return to the ground state while emitting visible light. However, the absorption coefficient of organic phosphors for X-rays is very low because of the low atomic number of the constituent atoms. Consequently the conversion efficiency of thin anthracene layers is low.

By separating the functions X-ray to secondary electron conversion and the secondary electron to visible light conversion (i.e. using the concept of composite product properties) the absorbed fraction

of the incident X-rays can be greatly enhanced by the incorporation of a dispersed second solid phase that consists (partially) of heavy atoms, such as PbCl_2 , and consequently exhibits a high absorption coefficient for X-rays. Therefore, at a given thickness of the composite layer the X-rays will be absorbed predominantly in the dispersed heavy phase, releasing secondary electrons. For X-rays of 100 keV energy these secondary electrons have a mean free path of the order of $10 \mu\text{m}$ in the dispersed phase. Consequently they spend most of their range in the anthracene matrix if the PbCl_2 particles are substantially smaller than $10 \mu\text{m}$. They excite the anthracene molecules, resulting in a luminescent emission output that can be an order of magnitude higher than in single-phase anthracene screens of equal thicknesses.

The backward emitted luminescent light was measured as a function of the thickness of the screen. Fig. 1 shows the measurement equipment; fig. 2 gives the experimental points and the theoretical curves. The latter are obtained taking into account the absorption of the X-rays and the generation, the absorption and the internal scattering of the luminescent light.

From fig. 2 it is evident that for screens of $400 \mu\text{m}$ thickness the amplification factor is 10 and increases to about 30 for thicknesses approaching zero.

Conversion of a magnetic signal into an electrical signal by means of a magnetoelectric composite material

A composite material having one magnetostrictive and one piezoelectric phase can exhibit a

magnetolectric effect. In this case the coupling of the Y quantity producing the Z/X effect is of a mechanical nature. Application of a magnetic field (X) induces a change in the shape of the magnetostrictive phase (Y), which in turn, through the mechanical coupling between the phases, causes a strain in the piezoelectric phase in which an electric field (Z) is generated.

In such magnetolectric composites the piezoelectrically generated charge will be compensated by leakage currents. This process can be characterized by a relaxation time τ :

$$\tau = \epsilon_0 \epsilon_{rel} \rho_c$$

where ρ_c is the resistivity and ϵ_{rel} the relative dielectric constant of the composite material. Consequently at frequencies higher than

$$\nu = (2\pi \epsilon_0 \epsilon_{rel} \rho_c)^{-1} \quad (1)$$

the loss of the generated electrical signal due to leakage currents will be negligible.

Recently ceramic magnetolectric composites have been prepared and investigated (18). Powders of the piezoelectric BaTiO_3 and the magnetostrictive NiFe_2O_4 were intimately mixed. The grain size was about 5 μm . The powder mixture was sintered at 1300°C for 24 h. Below this temperature these phases can coexist thermodynamically over a large temperature range and are therefore mutually nonaggressive. This offers the advantage that, within wide limits, the time and the temperature of sintering can be chosen such that a maximum mechanical coupling between the phases is obtained. In a number of cases the

composite samples were subjected to a second heat treatment in a controlled gas ambient in order to adjust the resistivity of the composite. Typical values for ρ_c and ϵ_{rel} measured in the poling direction at room temperature are $10^{10} \Omega \text{ cm}$ and 300 respectively, resulting in a lower limit for the working frequency according to eq. (1) of about 1 Hz. The samples were electrically poled by cooling them from above the ferroelectric Curie temperature in fields of 10 kV cm^{-1} .

The measured magnetoelectric effect at room temperature, $\Delta E / \Delta H$, was :

$$\Delta E / \Delta H = 10 \text{ mV cm}^{-1} \text{ Oe}^{-1}$$

at a magnetic bias field of about 400 Oe.

For sintered $\text{BaTiO}_3 - (\text{CoFe}_2\text{O}_4)_{1-x} (\text{Co}_2\text{TiO}_4)_x$ composite samples was found :

$$\Delta E / \Delta H = 3 \text{ mV cm}^{-1} \text{ Oe}^{-1}$$

at the same bias field.

These values, which are by no means optimum ones, were detected down to a frequency of about 1 Hz.

The crystallites of these ceramic magnetoelectric composites are randomly oriented. The $\Delta E / \Delta H$ values can be scaled up by means of crystallographic orientation and geometrical alignment of the finely intergrown constituent phases. A well-known technique used to obtain such composite structures is the unidirectional solidification of eutectic melts. In this way well-oriented magnetoelectric composites have recently been prepared, starting from the phase diagram of the quinary Fe-Co-Ti-Ba-O system (19,20). One phase is a magnetostrictive spinel and the other one a piezoelectric perovskite. In nearly all cases the crystallographic $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions of the

perovskite phase and the $\langle 100 \rangle$ directions of the spinel phase were parallel to each other, one of them being also parallel to the growth direction. A typical transverse section is given in fig. 3.

The structure of these in situ composites can be strongly influenced by varying the starting compositions. For example, a slight excess of TiO_2 can cause cellular structures as shown in fig. 4. Each cell consists of a large four-finned spinel dendrite surrounded by a eutectic structure of spinel and perovskite. The cell walls consist of perovskite and spinel with coarse precipitates of a third phase (magnetoplumbite).

The highest value of $\Delta E / \Delta H$ so far obtained at room temperature is :

$$\Delta E / \Delta H = 130 \text{ mVcm}^{-1} \text{Oe}^{-1}$$

down to $\nu = 5 \text{ Hz}$.

This value for the aligned composite should be compared with $20 \text{ mVcm}^{-1} \text{Oe}^{-1}$ for single-crystalline Cr_2O_3 , which is the single-phase material with the largest known magnetoelectric effect at room temperature.

From these figures it can be concluded that magnetoelectric composites are promising materials with many potential applications, for examples as sensors or monitors in apparatus and equipment with periodically moving parts.

The magnetoelectric composite material can be easily shaped by sawing, grinding and polishing. Fig. 5 shows a detection circuit for converting magnetic pulses into electrical pulses, based on a piece magnetoelectric composite of a few mm^3 and commercial circuit components.

Properties based on the morphology

Anisotropy

Some anisotropy aspects introducing new properties will be discussed referring to the InSb-NiSb eutectic composite. The InSb-NiSb system is a quasi binary one and exhibits a eutectic point (21). Unidirectional solidification of the eutectic melt (1.8 weight per cent NiSb) with a growth rate $R = 2 \text{ cm h}^{-1}$ yields the aligned composite material shown in fig. 6. It is composed of a disperse metallic NiSb phase, consisting of long hexagonal single-crystalline fibres of $1 \mu\text{m}$ cross section parallel to one another, and a continuous semi-conducting InSb matrix.

At room temperature the resistivity of the matrix is $\rho_m = 5 \times 10^{-3} \Omega \text{ cm}$, i.e. two orders of magnitude larger than that of the fibres. The electron mobility at room temperature is very high ($\mu_n = 63000 \text{ cm}^2 \text{V}^{-1} \text{sec}^{-1}$) but, because the hole mobility is almost 100 times smaller, the positive magnetoresistance effect in pure intrinsic single-crystalline InSb is small. Its resistivity increases only by a factor of 1.5 in an applied magnetic field of 10 kgauss, while a Hall voltage is produced at right angles to the directions of the electric current and the applied magnetic field. The effect is isotropic.

The magnetoresistance of the composite material (fig. 6), however, is considerably more pronounced, and, due to the alignment of the metallic NiSb fibres, strongly anisotropic (fig. 7). It is extremely large if the direction of the metallic rods, the electric current and the applied magnetic field are

mutually perpendicular to one another. In this arrangement the metallic NiSb fibres largely short-circuit the Hall voltage. As a result, the electrical current zig-zags through the composite. The zig-zagging is more pronounced if the applied magnetic field is stronger (22). If the magnetic field is increased therefore, the overall resistivity will increase sharply. A magnetic field of 10 kgauss was found to increase the resistivity by a factor of about 15 (fig. 8). This experimentally found factor is more than half the theoretically expected value for an infinite number of short-circuiting fibres. It far exceeds that of all existing single-phase materials.

Fig. 9. shows a design of the magnetoresistance device, a meander shaped fieldplate (produced by means of a photographic mask, a light-sensitive lacquer, and a suitable etchant), 25 μm thick and attached by means of an adhesive to an insulating substrate. Varying the shape has the effect of varying the resistance up to 125 Ω per square mm (without a magnetic field).

Apart from its uses for measurements of magnetic fields and as a contactless variable resistance and potentiometer (for example as a noncontacting nominal current indicator for the brake of an electrical locomotive (7)), the fieldplate can be applied in contactless control devices. The latter aspect was touched on in section 2 in connection with the magnetoelectric composite. However, there are pronounced differences. The magnetoelectric sample is an active device : it produces a direct electrical output when subjected to an alternating magnetic field. The field plate, on the contrary, is a

parametric device. Without extra energy supply it does not give an output when placed in a magnetic field. An electric current is needed for the read-out. Furthermore the resistivity of the magneto-electric device is many orders of magnitude higher than that of the fieldplate. Because of these and other differences the magnetoelectric device and the fieldplate will be supplementary devices for specific applications.

Interface

From single-phase materials it is known that internal interfaces can be the source of striking new properties. For example ceramic BaTiO_3 can exhibit an increase in resistivity above the ferroelectric Curie point of three orders of magnitude or more (23-25), which property is absent in single-crystalline BaTiO_3 (26). Similarly in a number of solid two-phase systems new properties have been found which appear to be related to the interface between the finely dispersed constituent phases. Examples are metal-glass resistive thick films and the voltage-dependent $\text{ZnO-Bi}_2\text{O}_3$ resistor.

Zero temperature coefficient of resistance.

Composite metal-glass thick ($5 \mu\text{m}$) films can be made in a wide range of sheet resistances. They are used in many applications, for example as stable resistors and potentiometers. Of special interest are the metal-glass composites with a very small temperature coefficient of resistance (TCR) in a wide temperature and resistivity range. Recently a study has been made of the d.c. conduction mechanism as related to the composite structure (27). The continuous

glass phase consisted of a lead boroaluminosilicate and the metal particles (Au) were formed by thermal decomposition of an organometallic solution. The final composite structure and the degree of dispersion is dependent on the composition and the temperature-time profile of the sintering process.

Composites with a metal to glass volume ratio of 0.1, the metal part consisting of Au with 13 at per cent Rh, and fired at 700°C, consist of a glass matrix with globular metal particles of the order of 10^{-2} μ m diameter, and exhibit a TCR = 0 between 30 and 300°K (fig. 10). The conducting part of this composite has been described as a system of small metal particles separated by very thin nonmetallic layers in which the conduction electrons are transported by means of quantum mechanical tunnelling (27).

No single-phase material can compete with this TCR = 0 composite.

Voltage-dependent resistance. Sintered ZnO is an n-type semiconductor with a hexagonal crystal structure of the wurtzite type and a resistivity of, for example, 1 Ω cm at room temperature. Sintering with small additions of Bi₂O₃ (0.5 mol per cent) increases the resistivity considerably. However, the electric current-voltage characteristic is then no longer linear. Above a given voltage the resistivity decreases with increasing voltage. Voltage-dependent resistors (VDR) are in use as surge suppressors (lightning arrestors, protection of contacts against sparking). The ZnO VDRs studied during recent years contain, besides Bi₂O₃, many more additives such as the oxides of Sb, Co, Mn, Cr and Sn (16, 28-31). A characteristic current-voltage curve is shown in

fig. 11. The region of the very steep rise of the current can be approximated by the relation

$$I/I_0 = (V/V_0)^\alpha$$

where I_0 , V_0 and α are constants (for example $I_0 = 1$ mA and V_0 the corresponding voltage). The commercial multicomponent VDRs (16, 28-31) have α -values of about 30. This value is higher than that of any single-phase material. V_0 can range from 100 V up to several kV. These values can be imposed by controlled sintering conditions and suitable design.

These multicomponent VDRs have at least five different phases between the ZnO grains, which complicates the study of the conduction mechanism. Fortunately recent investigations revealed that the simpler ZnO-Bi₂O₃-CoO system, consisting of only two phases: a ZnO and a Bi₂O₃-rich phase, showed essentially the same behaviour, α being 20 or more (32), which is evident from fig. 12. (The even simpler system ZnO-Bi₂O₃ has α -values as low as about 5 and was therefore not investigated further). Both phases contained some dissolved CoO (0.05 to 1 at per cent). Curves analogous to that of fig. 12 were obtained at temperatures deviating from room temperature. Capacitance measurements showed that the active insulating layer is not only the Bi₂O₃-rich phase, but that it includes a considerable part of the outer part of the ZnO grains.

In fig. 12 three distinct regions are clearly apparent: a linear, a square and an exponent $\alpha = 30$ current-voltage dependence. This behaviour has been described in terms of space charge limited current in an insulator with traps (29,32,33). Based on the

experimental results the following provisional conclusions were drawn (32) : The ZnO-Bi₂O₃ VDR consists of conductive ZnO grains surrounded by a thin, 0.15 μm thick, insulating layer with traps. The presence of Bi₂O₃ is essential during the formation of the insulating layer, though its nature has not yet been elucidated. The Co-dope is probably involved in the formation of the traps in the insulating layer. The fact that no square region is found in the more complicated systems might be ascribed to the presence of two or more different trap levels.

Conclusion

On the basis of a number of selected examples it has been shown that, besides their structural-mechanical potentialities, the composite materials exhibit new or advanced properties in various fields of physics. Considering the relatively small number of people working on non-structural composite properties, the results obtained so far may be qualified as spectacular.

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1. Equipment for measuring backward-emitted luminescent light. 1, X-ray tube; 2, sample; 3, cardboard tube; 4, photomultiplier; 5, lead shields; 6, power supply for the photomultiplier; 7, detector (after ref. 17).

2. Intensity of the backward-emitted luminescent light, J , in arbitrary units as a function of the thickness, D , of the sample. 1, the anthracene- PbCl_2 composite; 2, anthracene (saturated with PbCl_2). The squares correspond to single-phase PbCl_2 (After ref. 17).

3. Transverse section of a regular magnetoelectric composite. The dark phase is perovskite. X 200 (After ref. 19).

4. Transverse section of a magnetoelectric composite with aligned spinel dendrites. X 300 (After ref. 19).

5. Conversion of magnetic signals into electrical signals. 1, magnetoelectric composite material; 2, rotating disc with six magnetic pole pairs; 3, commercial IC with MOSFET input stage (Philips TAA 320).

6. The aligned InSb-NiSb eutectic composite.
a. Longitudinal section. X 200.
b. Transverse section. X 500.
(After ref. 21).

7. Relative resistivity (ρ_B / ρ_0) of the aligned InSb-NiSb composite as a function of the angle, θ , between current and magnetic induction B. At $\theta = 90^\circ$ the NiSb fibres and the magnetic induction are mutually perpendicular. (After ref. 21).

8. Relative resistivity (ρ_B / ρ_0) of the aligned InSb-NiSb composite as a function of the magnetic induction B . The electric current, magnetic field and fibres are mutually perpendicular (After ref. 21).

9. Fieldplate of InSb-NiSb eutectic composite
(After ref. 7).

10. Temperature-independent sheet resistance of a
metal-glass composite (see text) (After ref.27).

11. Current-voltage characteristic of a commercial VDR containing Bi, Sb, Co, Mn, Cr, Sn, B and Si as additives (After ref. 32).

12. Current-voltage characteristic of a ZnO-Bi₂O₃-CoO (0.5 per cent) VDR. (After ref. 32).

RAPPORTEUR'S REPORT

DESIGNING FOR NON-STRUCTURAL APPLICATIONS

AND PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

Session 5B

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The papers of this session cover a wide range of fields. I have attempted to divide the papers into a number of subjects which are listed below.

1. Conductivity (Thermal and Electrical) of Statistically Isotropic Composites
 - 1a - F. de Araujo, K. W. Garrett and H. M. Rosenberg - The Thermal Conductivity of Epoxy-Resin/Powder Composites from Liquid Helium to Room Temperature and of Indium Glass Composites.
 - 1b - B. Schulz - Thermal Conductivity of Composites.
 - 1c - F. de Araujo and H. M. Rosenberg - The Electrical Conductivity of Epoxy-Resin/Metal-Powder Composites.

2. Conductivity of Laminates
 - 2a - E. S. Kaczynski and G. Horvay - Thermal Response of Layered Composites.
 - 2b - G. Horvay and A. M. Manaker - Heat Flow in Laminated Composites Parallel to the Layering when the Surface Heating is of High Frequency.

3. Electrical Engineering Applications of Composites

3a - D. Stockel - New Aspects of the Use of Fibre-Reinforced Metals for Electrical Contacts.

3b - C.D. Skouby - Electromagnetic Effects of Advanced Composites.

4. Thermo-Elastic Properties of Composites

4a - J. A. Grubb and H. M. Rosenberg - The Thermal Expansion of Epoxy-Resin/Powder Composites from Liquid Helium Temperatures to 200°C.

5. Mechanical Properties of Composites

5a - A. Rotem and Z. Hashin - Fatigue Failure of Angle-Ply Laminates.

5b - M. F. Amateau, W. W. French, and D. M. Goddard - Friction and Wear Behavior of Metal-Matrix Graphite Fiber Composites.

A brief introduction to theory of conductivity of statistically homogeneous and isotropic composites will first be given. The subject is concerned with the following problem: Given a composite material which consists of two (or more) bonded homogeneous phases, which shall be assumed isotropic for reasons of simplicity, with conductivities μ_1, μ_2 respectively. The composite is assumed to be statistically homogeneous and isotropic and consequently its effective conductivity is characterized by a number μ^* which is a function of μ_1, μ_2 and the phase interface geometry. The problem is to determine μ^* analytically.

It is important to note that the problems of determination of effective dielectric constant, magnetic permeability, electrical and thermal conductivity are mathematically analogous.

The problem which has been stated is one of long standing and has been considered in many papers. It is of great importance to distinguish between exact, approximate and speculative treatments of the problem. For reviews in this sense see (1, 2). Here I shall only quote a few results which are of importance for this discussion. The first important result in the subject is due to Maxwell (3) who considered the case of a very dilute suspension of spherical particles in a matrix. Rayleigh (4) considered the case of a cubical array of identical spheres without Maxwell's restriction to dilute concentration by potential methods which involved some approximations. The calculations were refined by Meredith and Tobias (5).

Brown (6) considered the problem from a statistical point of view and showed that if the internal phase geometry is characterized statistically then μ^* is a function of the entire statistics of the phase geometry. For a recent review of statistical treatment see Beran (7).

Hashin and Shtrikman (8) showed that μ^* of any statistically isotropic two phase composite is bracketed by the bounds

$$\begin{aligned} \mu_{(-)}^* &= \mu_1 + \frac{v_2}{1/(\mu_2 - \mu_1) + v_1/3\mu_1} \\ \mu_{(+)}^* &= \mu_2 + \frac{v_1}{1/(\mu_1 - \mu_2) + v_2/3\mu_2} \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

$$\mu_{(-)}^* \leq \mu^* \leq \mu_{(+)}^* \quad \mu_1 < \mu_2$$

where v_1 and v_2 are the volume fractions of the phases. Moreover, the bounds (1) are best possible in terms of volume fractions. This means that in order to improve the bounds additional geometrical information, besides volume fractions must be used.

It is of importance to note that the bounds (1) are also exact solutions for μ^* of composites of special geometry known as composite spheres assemblages. Such composites consist entirely of geometrically similar composite spheres of different sizes, filling out all space in the limit, Fig. 1. Thus $\mu_{(-)}^*$ is μ^* of a composite spheres assemblage in which 1 is the matrix and 2 are the spherical particles, while $\mu_{(+)}^*$ is μ^* of the same kind of composite where 2 is the matrix and 1 - the particles.

Two important extreme cases are:

- 1) The particle conductivity is by an order of magnitude larger than that of the matrix (conducting particles, non-conducting matrix).
- 2) The particle conductivity is by an order of magnitude smaller than that of the matrix (conducting matrix, non-conducting particles).

It follows that:

$$\mu^* = \mu_m \frac{1 + 2c}{1 - c} \quad \mu_p \gg \mu_m \quad (2)$$

$$\mu^* = \mu_m \frac{2(1 - c)}{1 + c} \qquad \mu_p \ll \mu_m \qquad (3)$$

where μ_m and μ_p are matrix and particle conductivity, respectively, and c is particle volume fraction.

We shall now discuss the papers of the session.

Paper 1a

The paper presents an experimental investigation of the thermal conductivity of two types of composite materials. The first type consists of an epoxy matrix in which there are dispersed metallic particles of spherical or of irregular shape. The characteristic feature of this composite is that conductivity of the particles is by order of magnitude higher than matrix conductivity. The second kind of composite consists of an Indium matrix which contains glass spheres. In this composite matrix conductivity is by an order of magnitude higher than particle conductivity.

Measurements were performed at temperatures ranging from 20K to room temperature of 378K.

Authors state that there is a strong particle size effect at low temperatures. Representation of data for spherical copper, Fig. 2, with particle diameters ranging from $11\mu_m$ to $100\mu_m$ leads rapporteur to the opinion that the size effect is actually quite moderate relative to what is usually observed in composites. It should also be noted that what is classified here as size effect also incorporates the statistical effects of sphere dispersion in space.

Authors have compared experimental results for the metallic particle composites with the prediction of Meredith and Tobias (5) which has been discussed above. Fig. 2 shows experimental results with Meredith and Tobias curves.

Rapporteur has added the results of Hashin and Shtrikman (8) as expressed by the simple equ. (2). It is seen that up to volume fraction of about 45% the two theories are quite close and agree quite well with experimental data. At higher volume fractions the curves diverge. This happens for the following reasons: Meredith and Tobias dealt with a cubical array of equal spheres. In such an array the maximum attainable particle volume fraction is about 52%. In the composite spheres assemblage model of Hashin and Shtrikman 100% volume fraction of particles is attainable. Therefore, there must be considerable difference in conductivity values predicted by the two theories in the neighborhood of the maximum packing of spheres in a cubical array.

It must also be noted that the Meredith and Tobias calculation approximates infinite series by a finite number of terms. The accuracy achieved diminishes with decreasing distance between spheres, i.e. with increasing volume fraction.

Authors have not reported a comparison of the Indium matrix/glass spheres composite (conducting matrix/ non-conducting particles) with Meredith and Tobias results. Rapporteur has compared experimental results with equ. (3) and has not found good agreement.

Paper 1b

Author is considering conductivity of composites when the phase geometry is of irregular nature. Types of phase geometry are: particles which are approximately spherical, elongated chain-like regions and voids of similar shapes. Author uses a formula derived by Niesel for ellipsoidal particle shape which is based on "self-consistent" approximation.

The shape factor of particles is defined in terms of ellipsoids (of revolution). Mean shape factors of the composites used are determined by author on the basis of microphotographs of the composite by considering cuts of phase regions as equivalent ellipses.

Author considers the composites Bronze/Bakelite, U_3O_8/Al , La_2O_3/W , VO_2/Mo , VO_2/Cr , VO_2/Nb , Porous Alumina and obtains good agreement between measured and calculated conductivities.

Paper 1c

This paper is concerned with experimental investigation of Electrical conductivity of a composite consisting of epoxy matrix in which there are dispersed metallic particles. As has been pointed out in rapporteur's introduction, the analytical problems of prediction of electrical and thermal conductivities are identical. However, a special physical feature of electrical conductivity is the phenomenon of "switching". This phenomenon consists of a sudden decrease of resistance of the sample with increasing voltage. There are evidently two main factors which influence switching: the amount of voltage and the volume concentration of the particles.

The switching voltage is a decreasing function of the concentration and the switching concentration is a decreasing function of the voltage. Switching theory of composites is a difficult statistical problem and has so far not been treated with the same success as conductivity theories below switching voltage, which have been discussed in the introduction.

Author's measurements for a copper/epoxy material showed that at copper volume concentrations higher than 20% switching occurred at a few hundred volts.

Papers 2a,b

Authors consider analytically the transient thermal conductivity problem of a semi infinite laminate in which the edge is subjected to temperature input or heat flux input which is periodic in time.

The laminate consists of laminae of two different isotropic materials which are stacked in alternating fashion. The two different materials are designated "matrix" and "fibers". If by this is meant that the laminate is considered as a model for a uniaxially reinforced material then rapporteur would consider the geometrical approximation made to be of drastic nature. It would, however, be of interest to solve this problem for anisotropic layers in view of existing fiber composite laminates.

The analysis performed has yielded some curious results. For example: there is a flux singularity in the middle plane of the laminate; matrix and fiber fluxes do not enter from one material region into another. It would have been of interest to give temperature and flux profiles through laminate thickness with increasing distance from edge to laminate.

Paper 3a

Author discusses the technological aspects of use of composite materials, in particular fiber composites, for electrical contacts.

Requirements of a good contact material are: high conductivity, little burnoff, no welding effects, sufficiently good mechanical properties. The use of composites makes it possible to produce a wide choice of materials so that some with the desired properties can be obtained.

All composites discussed have a silver matrix which provides for high conductivity. Silver by itself does not have the desired properties for a contact material. It is too soft and has the tendency to weld together because of sparks.

The idea of using composites to improve properties of contact materials is not new. Composites used so far have been mainly of particulate and inter-penetrating types (Rapporteur: these are probably all statistically isotropic). Examples: Burnoff resistant AgW, CuW and AgMo. Introduced in World War II and used until now is AgCdO which has excellent anti-arching action. All of these are made by sintering processes.

Advantages of fiber-reinforced contact material over particulate or interpenetrating composite: better conductivity, better adhesion between phases, better mechanical properties (Rapporteur: in fiber direction), lower burnoff because of the better adhesion between constituents.

One good contact material consists of silver matrix with nickel fibers. Simple method of production consists of pressing together silver-clad nickel wires (shaping process). Other composite: Silver/graphite. About 5% graphite content produced by powder metallurgy. Subsequent extrusion produces graphite "fibers". Advantage of AgC - no welding of contacts. If particulate (sintered) there is high burnoff. However, if the graphite is fibrous, burnoff is reduced by a factor of 5. Rapporteur believes that it would be of great interest to explain this.

Author considers the economical aspects of the use of fiber reinforced contact materials (the production costs are high) and shows on the basis of "advantageousness factor" that fiber reinforced materials are more economical than sintered composites in spite of their higher production costs.

Paper 3b

The purpose of this work is to investigate experimentally the shielding provided by fiber composite material structures with respect to external electromagnetic sources and the capability of such composite materials to serve for ground planes of antennas. The motivation for the study is the increasing use of composite materials in aircraft. These materials are used for structural reasons but at the same time shielding requirements for the avionics system must be satisfied.

Shielding was determined for boron and graphite fiber composite panels and for certain structural elements by measuring the effect of the object on received signal strength for continuous wave signals. Antenna performance measurements were performed for various fiber composite ground planes. Gain, pattern and voltage standing wave ratios were determined for various frequencies.

Some of the more important results obtained are now listed :

1. Shielding measured for graphite fiber panels agreed with theoretical shielding results in terms of the effective electrical conductivity of the composite. In the case of boron fiber panels such agreement was not obtained. Author believes that this effect with boron is due to contact effects of the tungsten core of the boron fibers. Rapporteur does not consider this explanation convincing.

2. Various shielding results for box and frame structures are reported in the paper. Rapporteur finds it difficult to draw general conclusions from the effects which have been reported.
3. The major conclusion for antenna measurements is that composites form effective ground planes. There are only small performance differences due to replacement of metal ground planes by composite material ground planes.

Paper 4a

This paper is concerned with measurement of thermal expansion coefficients of composites which consist of a matrix and particles, and comparison of the results with theoretical predictions. Before entering into discussion of the paper it is necessary to quote some relevant theoretical results which have not been mentioned in the paper.

In a fundamental paper by Levin (9) it has been shown that the effective thermal expansion coefficient of a statistically homogeneous and isotropic two phase composite is related to its effective isothermal bulk modulus by the following formula

$$\alpha^* = \bar{\alpha} + \frac{\alpha_2 - \alpha_1}{1/K_2 - 1/K_1} \left(\frac{1}{K^*} - \frac{1}{K} \right) \quad (4)$$

where

$$\bar{\alpha} = \alpha_1 v_1 + \alpha_2 v_2$$

$$\frac{1}{K} = \frac{v_1}{K_1} + \frac{v_2}{K_2}$$

α_1, α_2 - phase thermal expansion coefficients

K_1, K_2 - phase bulk moduli

v_1, v_2 - phase volume fractions

K^* - effective bulk modulus

α^* - effective thermal expansion coefficient

This formula has been independently derived in (10, 11, 12) which also are concerned with other kinds of composites. An exposition of Levin's theory which was published in Russian is given in (12, 13).

Equ. (4) implies that if the effective bulk modulus is known analytically or experimentally, then the effective thermal expansion coefficient is also known.

An exact expression for the effective bulk modulus of a composite modelled by the composite spheres an assemblage, Fig. 1, has been given in (14). If this result for K^* is introduced into (4) there is obtained the expression for α^* which was derived by Fahmy and Ragai, (15), which has been quoted by the authors.

Authors have measured the thermal expansion coefficient of two kinds of composites: Epoxy matrix filled with spherical glass particles and epoxy matrix filled with alumina platelets. Temperatures of measurement ranged from 4 K to 293 K. It was found that for the Epoxy/glass spheres material best agreement was obtained with Fahmy and Ragai. As has been explained above this formula is an exact result for a certain arrangement of spherical particles. It is satisfying to note that experimental results fit best with the expression which has the best theoretical basis.

For the case of the epoxy/Alumina platelet material authors have found best agreement with the expression of Thomas. I consider this agreement to be fortuitous since as has been explained above the result of Thomas has no theoretical foundation. The correct way to proceed is to insert an expression for the effective bulk modulus K^* for the Epoxy/Platelet material into (4). Such an exact expression does not seem to be available. An approximate result has been given by Wu (16).

Paper 5a

This paper is concerned with prediction of fatigue failure of angle ply laminates for tension - tension cycling in the direction of the bisector of the angle between fibers.

In a previous paper (17) the authors established a fatigue failure criterion for single uniaxially reinforced laminae in plane stress. In the present work this failure criterion in conjunction with elastic stress analysis of the laminate is used to predict first failure of a lamina in the angle ply. Extensive fatigue tests for angle plies of different angles were carried out to examine if this first failure criterion could be used to predict fatigue failure of the angle ply. The material used was epoxy matrix reinforced by 65% volume of glass fibers.

The results obtained showed that for reinforcement angles between 45° to 90° first failure of lamina is very close to laminate failure while for reinforcement angles smaller than 45° the first failure criterion underestimates angle ply fatigue strength.

Paper 5b

Purpose of paper is to investigate friction and wear behavior of graphite fibre reinforced metals. Matrices used were: Al 201, Al 6061, Al A413, Copper and Tin. Fibers used were PAN based and rayon based: Thornel 50, Thornel 75 (Rayon), Thornel 300, Fortfafil 4R, Hercules A (PAN). Fiber volume fractions were 30%.

Fibers were coated by a thin deposit of titanium and boron by vapor deposition before immersion into the liquid metal.

Wear Tests were performed by pressing a specimen against a rotating steel wheel. Experimental procedure provides for a constant normal force on specimen which is independent of the amount of wear. Wheel mating surface velocity was 39.2 rad/sec corresponding to surface velocity of 0.684 m/sec. Wear was determined by computation of volume of wear scar which gives volume of specimen material lost because of wear.

Fiber orientation in specimens was normal or parallel to the wearing surface.

On the basis of the measurements performed authors have arrived at the following conclusions:

- a. The wear rates and friction are very much influenced by the type of fiber chosen: Composites containing rayon precursor fibers (high modulus, low strength) result in half the friction but with wear rates that are as much as an order of magnitude greater than those containing PAN precursor fibers (low modulus, high strength).
- b. Orientation of fibers with respect to the sliding direction does not influence the wear rates. (Rapporteur considers this a curious result which should be explained).
- c. In all cases but one graphite reinforcement improved wear and friction resistance.

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FIG. 1 - COMPOSITE SPHERES ASSEMBLAGE

FIG. 2 - THERMAL CONDUCTIVITY (K) vs VOLUME CONCENTRATION V_f

COMPARISON BETWEEN EXPERIMENT AND THEORY

- CUBICAL ARRAY OF SPHERES
- - - COMPOSITE SPHERES ASSEMBLAGE; BEST POSSIBLE LOWER BOUND.